

RELIABILITY ASSESSMENT AND IMPROVEMENT OF 11KV DISTRIBUTION SYSTEM WITH DISTRIBUTED GENERATION DEPLOYMENT

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ABSTRACT

Interruptions which are largely unavoidable contribute to the unavailability of power and the inability of the power system meeting the electricity demands of the consumers. The incessant interruptions and unstable power supply from the grid could be as a result of unreliable nature of the distribution system, which is unhealthy to the consumers, power system equipment and the utility company. Therefore, to minimize this unreliability issues, the power system planners need comes up with an upgrading approach with a view of improving the reliability of the distribution system. In this paper, reliability assessment of Okwuzi, Omoku 11kV distribution system was carried out using one year (January to December,2023) outage frequency and duration data gotten from the utility, in order to ascertain the reliability performance of the system by determining key reliability indices, and proposes penetration of distributed generation if the indices fail the set standard. Electrical Transient Analyzer Program (ETAP) software was used for the simulation. This was done by carrying out reliability study of the existing 11kV distribution network using embedded analytical equations in ETAP; reliability indices were determined, and improved upon by the penetration of PSO optimized distributed generation (1.63MVA) in bus 9 and reliability study was performed with DG. The results obtained indicate that when DG was injected into the system, average failure rate and average outage duration at load point 6, reduces by 34.2% and 23.8% respectively, then, so on up to load point 14. Similarly, at the penetration of DG, there were significant improvement in the customer's-oriented reliability indices; SAIFI, 0.4747 to 0.2535f/yr, SAIDI, 13.56 to 8.2585hr/yr, CAIDI, 32.577 to 28. 581hr.intr and EENS, 56.216 to 43.376MWhr/yr. The availability index ASAI improved from 86.8 % to 99.85% which is close to the 99.9989% IEEE benchmark.

KEYWORDS

PSO, Electrical Transient Analyzer Program, Distributed Generation, SAIFI, IEEE, ASAI

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Electrical energy plays an important role in the economy of any nation, so, there is need for an increase in the quantity of power supply in order to cater for the load requirement and create a competitive advantage for any country [1] [2]. Therefore, function of a power system is to supply all customers with electrical energy as economically as possible with an acceptable degree of reliability and quality [3]. In electrical power system, all

the generated electricity is consumed by the end users through the distribution system which is known as the last stage in the electric power delivery and is responsible to feed the electricity demand of all the consumers [4]. Distribution system is the connecting bridge between the transmission system and the consumers, assessing its reliability is paramount for smooth operation of the power system as a whole. Distribution system reliability can be defined as the availability or continuity of quality power supply for the consumer service entrance. A distribution system could be seen as reliable based on frequency of interruption, while not reliable in terms of duration of interruption, hence reliability has to be done both on the basis of interruption frequency as well as duration [5].

The poor performance or reliability of a distribution network is associated with outages, interruptions, failure, and unavailability, which are closely associated with switchgear/protection and control. A distribution system is said to be reliable, if its required function within a stipulated time period is met. Absolute (100%) reliability of distribution systems cannot be guaranteed. However, a very high level (about 99.9%) is aimed at and is being achieved in developed countries [6]. In developing countries like Nigeria, the electric power generated by available power stations do not match the units demanded by consumers [7]. The utility is characterized by suppressed demand due to the poor distribution system reliability inherent in the system [8]. Utility, therefore, considers load shedding as a way out to ensure that the available power from each of the distribution feeder from a network get to its respective consumers at any giving time, they choose for the customers which is inimical to the socio-economic growth and industrialization of the nation.

According to [9], distribution system account for about 90% of all customer reliability problems, and improving distribution reliability is to improve customer reliability and satisfaction. This reason arouses the interest for this study, to assess the reliability of a typical distribution system by determining the key reliability indices and propose a suitable improvement strategy such as; penetration of Distributed Generation (DG) in the system, if the results fall outside the acceptable statutory limit. This approach will aid in improving the overall reliability of the electrical network by reducing the associated system loss and thus, meeting the power demand of its consumers [10].

1.2 Statement of the Problem

The study case power distribution system (11kV distribution network of Okwuzi Community, Omoku in Rivers State) is characterized with high power losses, incessant daily power interruptions and increasing demand of electricity resulting to blackout and epileptic power supply in the area. The utility company (First Independent Power Limited) supplying electricity to the community only provides an average of five hours of electricity daily if there is supply, which is inadequate, it can even get worse by not providing electricity to the community for months due to unreliable state of the 11kV distribution system which feeds the area. This inadequate power supply results to social challenges for the residents of the community such as: lack of portable water, poor access to functional health care services, lack of quality education delivery and slow- down in commercial activities.

In order to meet up with day-to-day activities that require availability of power supply, consumers result to individual power generating sets, thereby solving the problem of power shortage only on a short-term basis. According to [11], for Nigeria to realize its goal of electricity for all, 70% of power required needs to be generated using distributed generation; basically, to reduce losses during transmission and distribution of electric power. This research seeks to evaluate the reliability of the study case, 11kV distribution system using

key reliability indices and propose the penetration of distributed generation (DG) into the network to maintain reliable, formidable and effective power system.

1.3 Aim of the Study

The aim of this research is to conduct reliability evaluation of 11kV power distribution system and propose its improvement through distributed generation deployment.

In order to achieve the aim of this study, the objectives outlined includes:

- i. To model the existing study case network using Electrical Transient Analyzer (ETAP) software and perform reliability study.
- ii. To determine the size and location to deploy Distributed Generation (DG) on the network using Particle swarm Optimization (PSO) technique.
- iii. To penetrate PSO optimized distributed generation into the distribution network, then, simulate again for reliability studies in ETAP.
- iv. To compare the reliability studies results with and without DG penetration to justify in order to justify the reliability improvement in distribution network.

1.4 Significance of the Study

If the outcome of this study is adopted and implemented, it will assist the utilities for proper system planning and operation to enhance reliable electric power supply for socio-economic growth and industrialization. Furthermore, the utility company providing power to the study area will gain more revenue as a result of improved supply of power to the consumers.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Brief Review of Related Works

Many researches have been conducted in relation to electric power distribution system reliability with different approaches suggested for its improvement. This research work is not an exception, but addition in the area of applicability. So, attempt is made to review relevant literatures on improving the overall reliability of the power system.

According to [12], presented a paper on the reliability evaluation and improvement of 11kV Karberey- Ramety Feeder II electric power distribution network. Reliability indices of the network of the network was computed using Failure Mode and Effect Analysis Technique, while a step-by-step economic analysis was used to determine optimum number and location of automatic switch fulfilling reliability and economic constraints. The results obtained show a significant reduction in customer's interruption cost.

According to [13], carried out a study on reliability optimization of a non-linear transmission network using Genetic Algorithm (GA) based optimization approach. The approach was tested on 33kV transmission feeders within Benin metropolis. The data of the network was used to determine the optimal performance of the feeders reliability and availability via minimization of downtime and Mean Time Between Failure (MTBF).The results obtained by authors shows an appreciable reduction in downtime, increment in MTBF, as well as improvement in reliability and availability of the network.

According to [14], presented a paper on the assessment of reliability of Cotobie distribution station in Ethiopia, with mitigation strategy using reclosers and disconnectors to minimize urgent and pressing power interruption. The results of the existing network frequency of interruption per year and average interruption duration violates the set reliability indices set by Ethiopian Electric Authority (EEA). When smart reclosers and disconnector design model was implemented, the reliability of the network improved significantly.

According to [15], carried out a reliability assessment of IEEE-RBTS BUS 6 distribution network. A standardized model of reliability system evaluation was constructed using Failure Mode and Effect Analysis (FMEA) table and the reliability is solved by combining Monte Carlo analysis method. The result obtained show that the method is effective and feasible to quantify the effect of distributed power supply on the reliability.

According to [16], conducted a study on the reliability assessment and enhancement of Dangila distribution system with distribution generation being placed at different distance from the supply point. The data from Dangila substation from 2020 to 2021 was used for the assessment. The results obtained by the authors show that as distributed generation was placed further from the supply point, the reliability of the power system improves more.

3.0 MATERIALS AND METHOD

3.1 Materials Used

Materials used in this research include Electrical Transient Analyzer Program (ETAP) software, Matrix Laboratory software (MATLAB), single line diagram of the study case network, cross-sectional area data of conductors, route length of the distribution line, one year outage data (January to December,2023) and number of customers on each feeder.

3.2 Method Used

The research method employed in this study is mainly analysis and simulation. Reliability studies of the existing network was carried out using analytical equations embedded in ETAP to determine load and customer’s-based reliability indices.

In order to minimize unavailability in the network, PSO technique implemented in MATLAB was used to determine the optimal size and location to place distributed generation on the network. Finally, reliability study was done again in ETAP with DG placement on the network

Tables 3.1, 3.2 and 3.3 show transformers and load data, average load outage data and line impedance of the network.

Table 3.1 Transformer and Load Data at Okwuzi. Omoku at 80% P.F

Bus ID	Transformer (MVA)	Input/Output (KV)	Unit	Load (MVA)
2 – 3	15	33/11	1	2.6
5 – 6	1	11/0.415	1	0.325
7 – 8	0.75	11/0.415	1	0.325
9 – 10	0.5	11/0.415	1	0.325
9 – 11	0.5	11/0.415	1	0.325
9 – 12	0.5	11/0.415	1	0.325
9 – 13	0.5	11/0.415	1	0.325
9 – 14	0.5	11/0.415	1	0.325

9 – 15	0.5	11/0.415	1	0.325
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Source: First Independent Power Limited (2023)

Table 3.2: Average Load Outage Data (January – December, 2023)

Substations Identification	Load (MVA)	Rated Voltage ratio	Outage Duration (Hrs)	Number of Interruption Customers	Total Number of Customers
T ₂	0.325	11/0415KV	183.6	186	522
T ₃	0.325	11/0415KV	205.16	124	731
T ₄	0.325	11/0415KV	188.205	177	669
T ₅	0.325	11/0415KV	312.53	199	751
T ₆	0.325	11/0415KV	366.11	202	973
T ₇	0.325	11/0415KV	268.33	179	833
T ₈	0.325	11/0415KV	105.32	139	791
T ₉	0.325	11/0415KV	361.74	147	942

Source: First Independent Power Limited (2023)

Table 3.3: Line Impedance

LINES ID	R (Ω)	X(Ω)
2 – 3	0.0558	0.04770
5 – 6	0.0495	0.05250
7 – 8	0.0660	0.07000
9 – 10	0.0082	0.0075
9 – 11	0.0825	0.08750
9 – 12	0.0330	0.03500
9 – 13	0.0247	0.02625
9 – 14	0.0165	0.01750
9 – 15	0.0330	0.03500

Source: First Independent Power Limited (2023)

3.2.1 Reliability Analytical Equations

The basic equations for calculating the reliability indices at each load point, P are as shown:

Average Failure Rate at load point, P,

$$\lambda_p = \frac{\sum f}{T} \text{ (f/yr)} \tag{3.1}$$

Where:

λ_p : Average failure rate at load point.

F: Load point failure (Frequency)

T: Operating time in hours

Annual Outage Duration at Load point, P,

$$\mu_p = \frac{\sum T_{dx}}{T} \text{ (hr/yr)} \tag{3.2}$$

Where;

μ_p : Annual outage duration at load point, P.

Tdx: Load point annual down time in hours

T: Operating time in hours

Average outage duration at load point, P,

$$rp = \frac{\mu_p}{\lambda_p} \text{ (hrs)} \tag{3.3}$$

Where:

rp : Average outage duration at load point, P.

μ_p : Annual outage duration at load point, P.

λ_p : Average failure rate at load point, P.

Customer’s based reliability indices are calculated using the basic load point indices like average failure rate, (λ), the average duration, (r) and the annual outage duration, (μ).

System Average Interruption Frequency Index,

$$SAIFI = \frac{\sum \lambda}{\sum N_T} \left(f / \text{cust} - \text{yr} \right) \tag{3.4}$$

Where:

$\sum N_T$: Number of customers connected to the load point, P.

System Average Interruption Duration Index

$$SAIDI = \frac{\sum \mu_T \cdot N_T}{\sum N_T} \left(\text{hr} / \text{cust} - \text{yr} \right) \tag{3.5}$$

Where:

μ_T : Annual outage duration at load point, P

$$CAIDI = \frac{\sum \mu_T \cdot N_T}{\sum \lambda_T \cdot N_T} \left(\text{hr} / \text{cust} - \text{yr} \right) \tag{3.6}$$

Average Service Availability Index,

$$ASAI = \frac{\sum N_T \cdot 0.760 - \sum \mu_T \cdot N_T}{\sum N_T \cdot 8760} \text{ (%) } \tag{3.7}$$

Average Service Unavailable Index,

$$ASUI = \frac{\sum \mu_T \cdot N_T}{\sum N_T \cdot 8760} \left(\text{hr} / \text{cust} - \text{yr} \right) \tag{3.8}$$

Expected Energy Not Supplied at Load Point, P.

$$EENs = \sum P_T \cdot \mu_T \text{ (Mwhr/yr)} \tag{3.9}$$

Where:

P_T : Average load of load point, P.

μ_T : Annual outage duration at load Point, P.

Equations 3.1 to equation 3.9 are the basic analytical method equations embedded in ETAP that are used to calculate the reliability indices considered in this study.

3.2.2 Particle Swarm Optimization Algorithm in Sizing and Placement of DG.

This research collaborated on a PSO algorithm that relied on a population-based randomized algorithm. The first object randomized swarm is considered the most promising (fitness) method, has been obtained to date and has already been maintained. The pbest value is used to represent such a result. The second most frequent

option is the global optimal, or gbest, which is assessed by the PSO compilers by watching the pbest readings and then setting both of the quantities. The particle's velocity is changed using Equation (3.10).

$$Vl_{x,y}^{new} = Vl_{x,y}^{old} - \alpha (random(k)) + \beta (Pr_{x,y}^{gbest} - Pr_{x,y}^{old}) \quad (3.10)$$

The old and new voltage are expressed as $Vl_{x,y}^{new}$ and $Vl_{x,y}^{old}$. The global best and old power value are denoted as $Pr_{x,y}^{gbest}$ and $Pr_{x,y}^{old}$. Here, random is a randomized variable with a value of 0 to 1, and α and β are acceleration coefficients. If the desired quantities are not discovered, Equation (3.11) updates the position.

$$Pr_{x,y}^{new} = Pr_{x,y}^{old} + Vl_{x,y}^{new} \quad (3.11)$$

The old and new power are denoted as $Pr_{x,y}^{old}$ and $Pr_{x,y}^{new}$. The new and updated voltage is denoted as $Vl_{x,y}^{new}$. When $x=1,2,3,\dots, N$ and $y=1,2,3,\dots, N$ are varied. More repetitions are required to reduce the inaccuracy to the point where the location can be determined in a single phase. The updated power is denoted in Equation (3.12).

$$Pr_{x,y}^{new} = (1-\alpha)Pr_{x,y}^{old} + \alpha Pr_{x,y}^{gbest} - \beta (random(k)) \quad (3.12)$$

α and β are acceleration coefficients, and the global best power is denoted $Pr_{x,y}^{gbest}$. The old and new power are expressed as $Pr_{x,y}^{old}$ and $Pr_{x,y}^{new}$. α runs between 0.1 and 0.5 and β runs between 0.1 and 0.7.

3.2.3 Problem Formulation, Objective Functions and Constraints.

The main objective of the optimal sizing and placement of distributed generation is to minimize total power active power loss in the distribution network with availability improvement.

The control variables are generators bus voltages and distributed generation source. The equality constraints are power/reactive power equalities, the inequality constraints include bus voltage constraints, generator reactive power constraints, and real or reactive power capacity constraints etc. The equality constraints can be automatically satisfied by load flow calculation, while the lower/upper limit of control variables corresponds to the coding on the Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) Algorithm, so the inequality constraints of the control variables are satisfied.

$$F = \min P_{loss} \quad (3.13)$$

$$P_{loss} = \sum_{k=1}^{ntl} G_k (V_i^2 + V_j^2 - 2 V_i V_j \cos(\delta_i - \delta_j)) \quad (3.14)$$

$$P_{loss} = \sum_{k=1}^{ntl} G_k (V_i^2 + V_j^2 - 2 V_i V_j \cos(\delta_i - \delta_j)) \quad (3.15)$$

Real power control variables:

- i. Distributed Generation
- ii. PV Bus

Constraints:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \Delta P_i \\ \Delta Q_i \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} P_i(V,\theta) - (P_{gi} - P_{di}) \\ Q_i(V,\theta) - (P_{gi} - P_{di}) \end{bmatrix} = 0 \quad (3.16)$$

Real Power Constraints:

$$i \in n,$$

where set of numbers of buses except the swing bus

2. Reactive Power Constraints:

$$Q_i(V, \theta) = \sum_{j=1}^{nbus} V_i V_j (G_{ij} \sin \theta_{ij} + B_{ij} \cos \theta_{ij}) \quad (3.17)$$

$$i \in n,$$

where set of numbers of buses except the swing bus

Bus Voltage magnitude constraints:

$$V_{i-min} \leq V_i \leq V_{i-max} \quad (3.18)$$

$i \in N$: Set of total buses

Generator bus reactive power constraint.

$$Q_{Gi-min} \leq Q_{Gi} \leq Q_{Gi-max} \quad (3.19)$$

$i \in \{N_{pv}, N_o\}n$,

Transfer Tap position constraints:

$$T_{i-min} \leq T_i \leq T_{i-max} \quad (3.20)$$

$i \in NT$

Where:

P_{loss} : System loss

N_b : Set of numbers of total buses

N_t : Set of numbers of tap-setting transformer branches

N_c : Set of numbers of possible reactive power source installation buses

N_{pv} : Set of numbers of PV buses

N_o : the swing bus

P_{Gi} : bus i real power supply

Q_{Gi} : bus i reactive power supply

P_{Di} : bus i real power load

Q_{Di} : bus i reactive power load

V_i : bus i voltage magnitude

θ_i : bus i voltage phase angle

θ_{ij} : Phase angle difference between bus i and j

G_{ij} : mutual conductance between bus i and j

B_{ij} : mutual susceptance between bus i and j

G_{ii} : self-conductance of bus i

B_{ii} : self-susceptance of bus i

q_{ci} : reactive power source i installation

TK : transformer k tap

$V_{i min}$, $V_{i max}$: bus I voltage limit

$Q_{Gi min}$, $Q_{Gi max}$: reactive source i reactive power limit

$T_{K min}$, $T_{K max}$: transformer k taps position limit

$q_{c min}$, $q_{c max}$: reactive power source installation capacity limit

4.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 Load Points Reliability Indices with and Without DG Penetration.

Figure 4.1 and Figure 4.2 show simulation diagrams of the test network without and with distributed generation penetration respectively. While, Figure 4.3 and Figure 4.4 depicts the comparison results of load point reliability indices (Average failure rate and average outage duration) with and without deployment of distributed generation in the network.

Figure 4.1: Simulation Diagram Without DG

Figure 4.2: Simulation Diagram with DG.

Figure 4.3: Plot of Average Failure Rate Versus Load Points

Figure 4.4: Plot of Average Outage Duration Versus Load Points

It is observed that by the integration of PSO optimized DG (1.65MVA) at bus 9, both the average failure rate and average outage duration reduced significantly. For load point 6, average failure rate decreased by 34.2 %, while the average outage duration decreased by 23.8 %. For load point 8, the average failure rate reduced by 35.2 %, while the average outage duration reduced by 24.99 % and so on up to load point 14.

4.2 Customer’s Based Reliability Indices with and Without DG Penetration.

Table 4.2 show result of customer’s-based reliability indices with and without penetration of DG.

Table 4.2: Customer’s Based Reliability Indices

Without DG		With DG	
Index	Value	Index	Value
SAIFI	0.4747f/cu.yr	SAIFI	0.2535f/cu.yr
SAIDI	13.56hr/cu.yr	SAIDI	8.2585hr/cu.yr
CAIDI	32.577hr/cu.intr	CAIDI	28.581hr/cu.intr
EENS	56.216MWhr/yr	EENS	43.376MWhr/yr
ASAI	0,868Pu	ASAI	0.9985Pu
ASUI	0.132Pu	ASUI	0.0015Pu

It is observed that existing system has a SAIFI value has 0.4747/cu.yr which means that the system has 0.4747 frequency of interruptions over the year, but when a DG of 1.63MVA is penetrated at bus 9, the SAIFI is decreased to 0.2535/cu.yr. This means that the system now has lower frequency of interruptions within a period of one year investigation

The existing system has a SAIDI value of 13.56hrs for each customer served for the one year under review. This is more than nine times the IEEE standard 1366-2003 which gives a value of 1.5 hrs for North America Utility. But when DG is penetrated, the SAIDI decreased to 8.2585hrs for each customer connected to the network for one year under investigation, although, the IEEE standard was not met, but there was an improvement. The existing system has a CAIDI value of 32.577hrs for customer interruption in a year, when DG is penetrated, the CAIDI reduced to 28.581hrs per customer interruptions. The existing system has EENS of 56.216MWhr/yr which mean that 56.216MWh of energy is not supplied by the system under the one-year investigation. But when DG is included in the network, the EENS reduced to 43.376 MWhr / yr which mean that 43.376 MWh of energy is not supplied by the system under the one-year review. Availability system reliability index, ASAI of the existing network was 86.8%, but when DG was connected, ASAI value improves to 99.85% which is very close to a value of 99.9989% that has been recorded for region that has sufficient power generation and robust system security.

5. Conclusion

The unreliable power supply in the distribution network has resulted to slowness in the socio-economic growth and industrialization of developing countries like Nigeria. The number of interruptions that happen and its duration while the electric power system performs its intended function is part of what determines the general reliability of the system; Therefore, it is significant to pay attention to the issue of distribution system reliability and devising approach(s) to improve it. This study assessed reliability performance in the 11kV Okwuzi, Omoku distribution network, with the intention of proposing its improvement through penetration of distributed generation (DG). Electrical Transient Analyzer Program (ETAP) software was used as the simulation tool. With the help of PSO algorithm implemented in MATLAB, the optimal size and location was determined for the proposed DG incorporation. When the PSO optimize DG was penetrated into the network, the system reliability indices such as: SAIFI, SAIDI, CAIDI and EENS were all improved upon significantly. System availability index, ASAI also improves from 86.8% to 99.85%. The incorporation of DG has proved to be an effective approach for reliability improvement in the distribution system.

REFERENCES

- Aioboman, A.E., Salau, A.O., & Chhabva, M. (2022). Review of the performance of the power sector in some selected African countries. IEEE Nigerian 4th International Conference, 17th – 19th May, Nile University Abuja, 1-5.
- Amuta, E., Wara, S., Agbetuyi, F.A., & Matthew, S. (2018). Smart grid technology potentials in Nigeria: An overview. *International Journal of Applied Engineering Research*, 13(2), 91-100.
- Andres, M.R., Armando, M.L.S., Jorge, L.J. & Jao, C.M. (2022). Static and dynamic aspects in bulk power system reliability evaluations, *IEE Trans. Power System*, 15(1), 189-195
- Olajuyin, E-A., Olulope, P., & Fasing, E.T (2022). An overview on reliability assessment in power systems using classic approaches. *Archives of Electrical Engineering*, 71(2), 425-443.

- Lin, X., Yufei, T., Gang, C., Chang, L- & Hug, C. (2020). Power supply reliability assessment of distribution network considering operation, maintenance and repair. *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, 440(2020), 1-7.
- Malik, A.A., Hussein, J.J., Bashar, S.F., & Baraq, M.A (2023) Power systems reliability assessment based on load shaping consideration. *TEM Journal*, 12(1), 291- 296
- Ikuobase, E., Olusegun, D. S., Mgbemena, C. O., & Adeyeri, M.K. (2018). Electric power generation crisis in Nigeria. A review of causes and solutions. *International Journal of Integrated Engineering*, 10(1), 47 - 56.
- Akhikpemelo, A., Eyibo, M.R., & Adeyi, A.A. (2016) Reliability analysis of power distribution network. *Continental Journal of Engineering Science*, 11(2), 53-63
- Kabi, R. P., Ash-Bahadur, S., Kezang, P. & Roshan, K. (2020). Reliability assessment of distribution system. *International Research and Engineering Development*, 3(4), 1-9
- Martinez-Velasco, J.A. & Guerra, G. (2016). Reliability analysis of distribution system with photovoltaic generation using a power flow simulator and a parallel Monte Carlo Approach, *Energies*, 9(7), 537-539.
- IEA. (2019). International energy agency. Renewable information. Overview IEA Paris. Retrieved from <https://www.iea.org/reports/renewables-information-overview> .
- Pri, K.R., Subba, A.B., Pelden, K., & Chhetri, R. (2020). Reliability assessment of distribution system through FMEA analysis. *International Journal of Scientific Research and Engineering Development*, 3(4), 560-565.
- Airoboman, A.E. & Ogujor, E.A. (2020). Reliability optimization on power systems network using genetic algorithm. *Journal of Electrical, Control and Technological Research*, 2(3), 18-29
- Seada, H. & Kemal,I.(2020).Assessment of distribution system reliability and mitigation by using reclosers and disconnectors: The case of Cotobie distribution station. *International Journal of Innovative Research in Applied Science and Engineering (IJIRASE)*, 4(5), 774-784.
- Choa, C., Zhenjian, X., Haofei, C., Jun, H., Anjie, F. & Ha, W. (2021). Study on reliability assessment of distribution networks containing distributed power supplies. *Journal of Physics Conference series*, 2030 (2021), 1-8.
- Mamo, A. & Hizkiel, A. (2023). Reliability assessment and enhancement of Dangila distribution system with distributed generation. *Cogent engineering*, 10(3), 3 -10.